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The Impact of Policy Interventions on Young People's Digital Skills Development: A Simulation Approach

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Please cite this report as:

Song, H., Boomgaarden, H., Tolochko, P., & Kronschnabl, H. (2023). *The Impact of Policy Interventions on Young People's Digital Skills Development: A Simulation Approach*. KU Leuven: ySKILLS.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 870612. The information in this deliverable reflects only the authors' views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

Public

Project: ySKILLS – Youth Skills
GA: 870612
Call: H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-07-2019
Type of action: RIA

The Impact of Policy Interventions on Young People's Digital Skills Development: A Simulation Approach

Work Package 5 – Deliverable 5.3

Due date: 31 August 2023
Submission date: 31 August 2023
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Executive summary

Digital skills are increasingly recognized as crucial for young peoples' academic and labour market success. While it is often assumed that young children and adolescents would pick up digital skills on the go, unequal distributions of digital skills continue to exist. This observation emphasizes the need for policy interventions to ensure equal opportunities for all young individuals in digital skills developments and related academic and labour market success, as well as their online opportunities and wellbeing. This report aims to shed light on the dynamics of digital skill developments among children and adolescents at their early stage of development (e.g., aged 11–17), which represents critical and formative stage of one's digital skills and wellbeing. More importantly, it tests the effectiveness of intervention programmes that aim at improving digital skills with a focus on testing their effects on particularly vulnerable (“at-risk”) groups, meaning less digitally skilled and therefore disadvantaged due to their poor mental health, ethnic or cultural origin, socioeconomic status and gender.

Since implementing intervention programmes is costly and real-life contexts should and cannot be used as experimental playgrounds, we implement a series of computer simulation-based approaches where we programme an artificial society of autonomous “agents” with rules of behaviours, and observe their collective behaviours and outcomes as a function of several principled intervention scenarios. We argue that our computer simulation-based approach offers relevant evidence to assess the effectiveness of intervention programmes. The model serves as a foundation for informed decision-making and the development of evidence-based interventions. The focus was on whether interventions would lead to an overall increase in digital skills as compared to the baseline model, and more importantly, whether interventions would be effectively reducing the gap between students who, at the outset, were less likely to further develop their skills versus those who would likely show increasing skill levels.

In this report, three types of intervention programmes were considered: those improving access to ICT hardware, network, and digital skills and literacy training (affecting the opportunity structure to acquire digital skills), and those enhancing students' receptivity and motivation to acquire digital skills. We program these interventions based on the ySKILLS panel survey (see e.g., [D5.2](#)).

The simulation models clearly showed that interventions focusing on students' receptivity to learning and acquiring digital skills were the most successful in closing digital divides, surpassing programmes aimed solely at improving access opportunities. In conclusion, investing in targeted structures and programmes to encourage receptivity to digital skills development is more effective than costly interventions that improve access for all or the more vulnerable.

1 Introduction

1.1 The ySKILLS project

The ySKILLS (Youth Skills) project is funded by the European Union (EU's) Horizon 2020 programme. It involves 16 partners from 13 countries to enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the information and communications technology (ICT) environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for children and young people by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills. Starting from the view that children are **active agents in their own development**, ySKILLS examines how digital skills mediate the risks and opportunities related to ICT use by 12–17-year-olds in Europe (see <https://yskills.eu>).

The overarching aim of ySKILLS

To enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the ICT environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for all children by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills.

ySKILLS will **identify the actors and factors** that undermine or can promote **children's wellbeing** in a digital age. The relations between ICT use and wellbeing will be critically and empirically examined over time.

ySKILLS' research objectives

To acquire extensive knowledge and better measurement of digital skills.

To develop and test an innovative, evidence-based explanatory and foresight model predicting the complex impacts of ICT use and digital skills on children's cognitive, physical, psychological and social wellbeing.

To explain how at-risk children (as regards their mental health, ethnic or cultural origin, socioeconomic status and gender) can benefit from online opportunities despite their risk factors (material, social, psychological).

To generate insightful evidence-based recommendations and strategies for key stakeholder groups in order to promote European children's digital skills and wellbeing.

ySKILLS has proposed, and will continue to develop, its **conceptual model** (see Figure 1):

1.2 Background and theoretical approach

In the digital age, technology has become an integral part of our daily lives, profoundly transforming the way we work (Aroles et al., 2021), communicate (Giannoulis & Wilde, 2019), and access information. The digital revolution continues to transform the job market, with an increasing emphasis on digital competencies (Oberländer et al., 2020; Periañez-Cañadillas et al., 2019). Digital skills, such as coding, data analysis, or digital marketing, are becoming increasingly indispensable for a wide range of professions, from traditional sectors to emerging fields. Individuals with strong digital skills are better equipped to meet the evolving demands of the labour market, as they possess the agility and proficiency necessary to thrive in a continuously changing digital landscape. Therefore, nurturing and fostering digital skills among young people is crucial for their labour market achievements and long-term career prospects. For increasing the prospects of young people to successfully enter the labour markets of the future, digital skills may play a significant role.

At the same time, digital skills have become increasingly intertwined with academic and school achievements and it has been suggested that digital skills are positively related to academic achievements of young people (Hurwitz & Schmitt, 2020; Kim, Hong & Song, 2019). The ability to effectively use and communicate via digital tools, access and evaluate online resources, or critically navigate digital platforms may be crucial for students to excel in their academic pursuits. Students proficient in digital skills have been shown to have higher levels of engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. Moreover, digital skills enhance students' capacity to adapt to new learning environments, such as online or blended learning models (Wardani et al., 2019). Digital skills also foster creativity and digital literacy, enabling students to navigate the vast amount of information

available online while discerning reliable sources. Ultimately, digital skills equip students with the necessary competencies for success in a digitally-driven world.

Yet, while digital skills offer immense potential, it is crucial to understand unequal distributions of digital skills among children and adolescents. Digital divides (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2011) continue to characterize how some benefit while others are left behind. While in many cases such digital divides are not anymore characterised by differential access to Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) (economic divide), in particular among young people, they nowadays manifest more likely in terms of differences of abilities to actually effectively use ICTs (usability divide) and arguably even more so in the empowerment divide thereon (Lythreatis et al., 2022). It is commonly argued that young people would pick up digital skills on the go nowadays, given that they are growing up in a highly digitalized environment (Helsper & Eynon, 2010). However, digital divides continue to exist (Chen & Wellman, 2004), also among the young (Eynon & Geniets, 2016). Disparities in access to technology and in digital literacy training can exacerbate existing educational inequalities (Ritzhaupt et al., 2020) and leave behind particularly vulnerable and disadvantaged groups of young people. This observation emphasizes the need for targeted interventions to ensure equal opportunities for all young individuals in digital skills developments and related academic and labour market success.

1.3 The aims of this report

Given the rapid advancement of digital technologies, it is crucial to promote digital skills among young people. This report aims to shed light on the dynamics of digital skill developments among children and adolescents, with a primary focus on evaluating the effectiveness of intervention programmes that aim at improving digital skills, especially for vulnerable (“at-risk”) groups, meaning less digitally skilled and therefore disadvantaged due to their poor mental health, ethnic or cultural origin, socioeconomic status and gender (see D6.1 for details). We assess the extent to which three types of intervention programmes can narrow the gap in digital skills between more and less vulnerable groups. Our main considerations lie in whether such interventions provide for a more conducive environment for digital skills development and/or affect youth’s receptivity towards learning and improving skills. To fully harness the benefits of digital skills, policymakers must prioritize integrating digital literacy and computational thinking into formal education systems while also ensuring access to both formal and informal learning opportunities. Policymakers can collaborate with schools, community organizations, and private sector stakeholders to provide affordable access to digital resources and training opportunities, in particular for underserved groups.

To comprehensively understand the complexity of factors affecting digital skills developments and the potential impacts of policy interventions, this report draws on a series of simulation models that consider dynamics of digital skill developments among different groups of more or less vulnerable young people over the course of a simulated period of three years. It then applies three concrete interventions that should affect digital skills developments and pays particular attention to narrowing or widening digital divides. Given that directly implementing multitude of large-scale intervention programmes is extremely costly, involves lots of uncertainties, and potentially pose serious ethical constraints (i.e., that real life contexts should and cannot be used as experimental playgrounds), we argue that our simulation approach offers relevant evidence to assess the effectiveness of intervention programmes. That is, our simulation-based approaches enable us to flexibly yet effectively capture complex emergent phenomena while bypassing most of the logistical challenges involved on direct implementation of complex, large-scale interventions in a real-world context. The model serves as a foundation for informed decision-making and the development of evidence-based interventions.

1.4 Agent-based modelling methodology

Agent-based modelling (ABM) is a computational modelling approach that simulates the behaviour and interactions of autonomous individual entities – formally referred to as agents – within a given biological or social system (Axelrod, 1997). Each agent (representing agency of actions) possesses unique characteristics, rules, and decision-making capabilities, allowing them to act independently, influence and be influenced by their environment. ABM provides a powerful tool for studying complex social systems, as it enables the examination of emergent phenomena that arise from the interactions among individual agents. In the context of understanding the digital skills among children and adolescents, ABM offers a valuable approach. Agents can be programmed to engage in various activities based on some predefined rule of behaviours, such as learning from and interacting with peers and from their social surroundings, seeking or providing advice, and navigating digital content. These activities can be influenced by factors such as the agent’s own digital skills levels, their social surroundings like social networks, individual difference factors such as demographic characteristics, and the influence of peers, which in turn recursively shaping their digital skills over time. By running simulations using ABMs, researchers can observe and analyse the individual- as well as system-level emergent patterns of digital skills as outcomes that arise from the interactions among agents and as a result of policy intervention programmes. By incorporating empirical data and evidence-based assumptions into the model, policymakers can assess the potential impacts of different policy interventions before implementing them in the real world. This allows for evidence-based, informed policy decisions that are grounded in a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics of ICT use and digital skills and academic performance of children and adolescents (see later “2.4 Interventions” for more details).

When exploring possible policy interventions related to the impacts of ICT use and digital skills on the wellbeing of children and adolescents, three specific strategies are considered. *First*, we consider an intervention focussed on the economic dimension of digital divides in terms of improving the technical infrastructure of access to ICT resources in schools in terms of the provision of hardware (subsidized devices), network access (internet connectivity in school and at home) as well as educational tools and learning platforms (access to mobile learning solutions). It is reasonable to assume that improved hardware access will be particularly important for economically disadvantaged groups. *Second*, we look at the usability dimension of digital divides in that we consider the effectiveness of a strong implementation of ICT training and digital literacy programmes in formal educational settings. This includes training teachers to develop their own skills and administer training and literacy programmes. This integration can contribute to students’ development of technical and critical skills, by helping them to improve their technical abilities and information literacy, as well as develop critical thinking skills and digital competence. *Third*, we consider an aspect that pertains more to the empowerment dimension of digital divides among youth. Here we consider how peer support and peer mentoring could improve digital skills among peer group members. Peer-led initiatives or mentoring programmes can facilitate knowledge sharing, provide guidance on responsible ICT use, and offer support in navigating the digital world outside of the more formal educational settings.

The three types of intervention programmes can be categorized based on their objectives: the first aims to enhance opportunity structures, the second targets increasing youth’s receptivity, while the third, usability-focused intervention, falls somewhere in between. We use our simulation models to assess the potential effectiveness of such intervention programmes on closing the gaps in development of unequal distributions of digital skills (i.e., reducing systematic disparities in digital skills between less vs. more vulnerable groups of children and adolescents). It is vital to understand whether interventions have the potential to bridge the gaps between the more and the less skilled. By

relying on our models, we can provide relevant input into the concrete building and implementation of interventions in real-world scenarios.

2 Digital skills and digital divides

This report provides the insights generated from a simulated environment. It is important that such simulation models are informed by and hence modelled after theoretical and empirical evidence generated through prior research. In this section we provide a short overview of relevant literature and findings. As specified further below, in addition to this, our model heavily builds on the empirical evidence generated through the ySKILLS panel survey (see e.g., [D5.2](#)).

2.1 What are digital skills?

The general definition of digital skills used in this report is consistent with the definition used throughout the ySKILLS project. Digital skills are therefore described according to the Telecommunication Union's (ITU) definition, as “the ability to use ICTs in ways that help individuals to achieve beneficial, high-quality outcomes in everyday life for themselves and others” and to “reduce potential harm associated with more negative aspects of digital engagement” (Helsper & van Deursen, 2018, p. 23). Definitions of digital skills were originally characterized by a limited technical and functional focus, as is common in a political science and information science discourse, and are now shifting toward a stronger focus on critical, evaluative competencies, which are mentioned more frequently in the pedagogical and media education literature (Helsper et al., 2020, van Laar et al., 2022). Functional, technical aspects refer to people's ability to use the functions of ICT, and critical aspects refer to people's understanding how and why ICTs are designed and content is produced in particular ways (van Laar et al., 2022). Though varying definitions of digital skills regarding a technical or critical focus can be found in the academic literature, there is a relative consensus that digital skills can be divided into broad categories such as technical, informational, social, and creative skills (Ba et al., 2002; Helsper, 2008; Van Deursen & Van Dijk, 2008). Helsper et al.'s (2020) recently developed framework for dividing digital skills into sub-skills builds on these initial categories and identifies four dimensions: (1) technical and operational skills; (2) information navigation and processing skills; (3) communication and interaction skills; and (4) content creation and production skills. In addition to these four dimensions, programming skills are also included as a single, fifth element in their framework (Helsper et al., 2020).

2.2 Which factors affect the development of digital skills?

A considerable amount of empirical studies have engaged with the question why some children and adolescents have higher digital skills levels than others (for a comprehensive review, see [ySKILLS D2.1](#)). Overall, some factors consistently show a relationship with children and adolescents acquiring or holding more digital skills. Among these main factors are sociodemographics such as age, gender, education, yet also the extensive use of digital technologies. Older children tend to have better digital skills since they have had more time and opportunities to acquire these. Gender appears to be a factor in self-reported skill levels, with boys often claiming to hold better digital skills (for details, see e.g., [D.2.1](#) and [D.2.2](#)). This finding, however, is not consistently supported by actual performance tests. Both better cognitive skills but also better academic achievements appear to be related to higher digital skills. Finally, positive attitudes towards digital technologies, which lead to increased usage, also relate to holding better digital skills, a relationship that seems quite plausible.

As evident from the above, there is a strong focus on looking at individual capacities rather than considering contextual aspects when studying the digital skills of children and adolescents. Yet, children and adolescents are embedded in multiple social structures (Jenks, 2004) and it is reasonable to assume that these social embeddings do reflect on the acquisition, maintenance, and sharing of digital skills. Adopting such a social structural perspective, which differs from the more common individual-focused perspective on adolescents' digital skills acquisition, joins more recent literature in the field that emphasises the role of networks and spaces when it comes to people's engagement with digital technologies (Helsper, 2021). Some extant literature, however, does provide rationales and insights on three types of social structures by means of looking at the impact of factors related to family contexts and schools, and to a lesser extent to peer networks (see also [ySKILLS D2.1](#), pp. 61-73).

In the literature acknowledging the effects of social structures, the main focus is on the influence of family structures. Prior research has, for instance, shown that the socio-economic status (SES) of parents in terms of education levels, household incomes or parents' occupations does relate to children's skill levels (for a summary, see [D2.1](#), p. 61). Higher parental or family SES is often positively related to skill levels. Another factor is parental mediation of the use of digital media and resources (for a summary, see [D2.1](#), p. 63). The literature distinguishes between enabling mediation, which refers to parents talking to children about what they are doing online, enabling online activities or and giving advice as to how to safely navigate online environments, and restricting mediation, which basically relates to limiting the time of usage of digital technologies (Livingstone et al., 2017). Additionally, children and adolescents spend substantial amounts of time in school, and schools can play a crucial role in reducing disparities caused by socioeconomic backgrounds. As outlined in [D2.1](#) (pp. 66-69) it appears useful to distinguish between factors that relate to teachers, to the types of information about and experiences with information and communication technology (ICT) that students have at school and to the school environment itself. There is only marginal evidence suggesting that teachers' attitudes towards and skills related to ICT use have an effect on school children. Overall, experiences with ICT in a school environment tend to be positively related to digital skills, yet the evidence is not uniformly pointing into this direction. Generally the literature supports the usefulness of schools making investments into integrating ICT experiences for their students. Again, while it is reasonable to assume that the social structure offered in schools would be an important factor, the available evidence is mixed.

Thus far, there has been rather little research looking at the influence of peers on digital skills acquisition. Adolescence is a critical period in which strong ties with peers are developed and maintained, and peers play a significant role in adolescents' daily interactions. The potential for peer interactions is also increased through the digital environment. Extant studies that have looked at peer influences (for an overview see [D2.1](#), p. 70) paint an overall positive picture. Peers seem to be helpful in terms of informally teaching and learning digital skills from each other and hence passing on or co-developing skills. Using digital technologies together with peers does promote digital skills and this seems to be even more pronounced when doing so with close friends. Particularly schools ensure that children and adolescents have a multitude of regular social contacts (which could be further extended through leisure time activities) and are embedded in peer networks (see also [D5.1](#)).

2.3 Peer Inequalities in digital skills

As outlined above, when it comes to explaining the extent to which people can be defined as digitally skilled, the breadth of ICT use or experience, gender, and level of education are very important

factors, in some cases even more important than generational differences (Helsper & Eyon, 2010). Young people who have relatively good access to the internet, strong support networks, and life circumstances in which Internet use is both facilitated and rewarded are more likely to learn and improve digital skills as they broaden their experiences (Eynon & Geniets, 2016). Young people with less favourable circumstances lack this immersion in a digital environment, meaning that they do not have the opportunity to pursue a breadth of activities online in their daily lives to learn and improve their interactions with technology (Helsper & Eyon, 2010). These disparities in digital skills are referred to in the literature as digital divides, which are manifested in divides of physical internet access and divides including the different skills for using the internet (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2010). According to Lythreath et al. (2022, p. 1), the digital divide refers to inequalities “in Information and Communications Technology access, usage, and outcome.” This definition reflects the three levels of the digital divide: the first level of the digital divide pertains to the binary distinction between people with and without Internet access (economic dimension; Dewan & Riggins, 2005); the second level of the digital divide includes not only access but also differences in the use of digital capabilities such as usage behaviour, usage autonomy, or technical means (usability dimension; Dewan & Riggins, 2005; Lythreath et al., 2022), and the third level of the divide considers the outcomes of Internet use and whether the results are beneficial to the user, in addition to other relevant factors (empowerment dimension; Wei et al., 2011).

Several studies (Balea, 2016; Eynon & Geniets, 2016; Zhong, 2011) show that there is a first-level digital divide in terms of access among young people. According to in-depth interviews conducted by Eynon and Geniets (2016) with digitally excluded young people, poor access to technology and limited support networks prevent these young people from gaining the experiences they need to develop digital skills and perceive the Internet as valuable to their lives. However, Zong (2011) noted that higher levels of technology penetration do not guarantee that young people will have more opportunities to learn and use these technologies, as digital skills at the individual level are also influenced by gender, economic status, and their experiences with the tool. This second-level digital divide is also found in Balea’s (2016) study, in which even when private access to a smartphone, mobile internet use, and the number of years children’s experience using a cell phone are taken into account, children still report different levels of digital skills depending on their age and gender. Accordingly, a gender gap can also be observed in studies on digital skills, as boys usually report higher digital skills than girls (Balea, 2016; d’Haenens, 2021; Mascheroni et al., 2022). If the effect of age on digital skills is also taken into account, study results show that older boys are the most competent children in using digital devices (Balea, 2016).

2.4 Interventions

To our knowledge, there is only a very limited number of studies in the field of children’s and a major aim of our report is to simulate what would happen to digital divides among young people if different intervention programmes were to be implemented with the goal to narrow digital skill divides between the more and less digitally skilled ones. As discussed above, our social realities seldomly offer the opportunity to experiment with costly intervention programmes without initial evidence of their effectiveness. Also it is ethically at least questionable to roll out such intervention experiments on a large scale given that they may yield differential and unforeseen effects. Therefore we consider this report as *setting the stage for using social simulation approaches* to provide evidence that may be the basis of policy making and real world implementation of intervention programmes.

We differentiate between two types of impact that three intervention programmes may have and that then may affect the further development of digital skills and the potential narrowing of digital divides,

as described in Table 1 below. These two types of impact arguably reflect on different dimensions of digital divides as discussed above.

Table 1. FOCUS OF INTERVENTIONS AND THEIR LIKELY OUTCOMES		
Likely Outcomes on...	Opportunity Structure	Receptivity
Interventions Focusing on....		
(1) Improving Access	+	
(2) Receptivity & Motivations		+
(3) Peer-based learning	+	+

In below description of interventions, we consider interventions that affect the *opportunity structures* of youth to acquire digital skills, by improving their access to hardware, software or training programmes. Second, we look at interventions that may affect the *receptivity* of youth towards taking up the opportunities to acquire digital skills, that is to what degree they positively respond to what is offered to them or to what they have access to. Based on this distinction, below we model the effects of three more concrete types of intervention programmes.

First, we consider the *economic dimension* of digital divides and test interventions that would increase access to ICT in terms of *hardware infrastructure and connectivity*. Ensuring that schools and students have the necessary infrastructure and reliable internet connectivity is essential for effective ICT integration. This includes providing sufficient hardware, such as computers, laptops, or tablets, and establishing a robust network infrastructure to support the technological needs of students and teachers. It is argued that ensuring equitable access to ICT resources is crucial to bridge the digital divide and promote equal opportunities for all. Initiatives such as subsidized devices, internet connectivity programmes, or mobile learning solutions may help address the disparities in ICT access among students. Hence this first intervention tests the effectiveness of improving the opportunity structure in terms of hardware and network connectivity. It could be assumed that all students would benefit from improved opportunity structures, but the disadvantaged are especially more likely to be benefited given their stronger need for improved access.

Second, we consider the implementation of focussed *ICT training and digital literacy programmes* in school curricula. This particular type of intervention is arguably more focussed on the *usability dimension* of digital divides and aims at promoting actual usage skills. It on the one hand improves an opportunity structure for learning, but may also increase students' receptivity to wanting to acquire digital skills by demonstrating their relevance. Integrating digital skills training across various subjects and disciplines can enhance learning outcomes and promote interdisciplinary connections. By incorporating digital tools and online resources into different subjects, students can experience the relevance and applicability of ICT in their everyday lives. This integration may help students develop critical thinking skills, information literacy, and digital competence across multiple domains. Implementing comprehensive digital literacy programmes within educational settings may equip children and adolescents with the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate the digital world effectively. By enhancing digital literacy, students may develop a better understanding of the potential risks and benefits of ICT use. We assume this intervention to be particularly focused at the group of vulnerable, less digitally skilled students.

Third, we test an intervention that reasonably could be considered to connect to the *empowerment dimension* of digital divides. Specifically, we test whether establishing and rewarding *peer learning structures* within school environments would narrow digital skill divides. Here we consider whether creating an environment which demonstrates the relevance and usefulness of digital skills and doing so based on the observation that peer networks and peer learning appear effective for skills acquisition would lead to narrow skill divides. This intervention is thought to particularly affect the receptivity of students to learn. Creating opportunities for peer support can be valuable in enhancing digital skills and promoting positive social interactions. Peer-led initiatives can facilitate knowledge sharing, provide guidance on responsible ICT use, and offer support in navigating the digital world. Peer support can contribute to a sense of community, foster positive social connections, and help individuals develop resilience against potential challenges in the digital sphere.

We have developed various concrete simulation models that encompass different perspectives on the purpose and potential outcomes of policy interventions as discussed above. These models consider different scenarios for enhancing digital skills through policy measures, where we later on compare relative effectiveness of those interventions in reducing systematic disparities in the distribution of digital skills. Specifically, the simulation models include the following approaches:

1. Model 1 focuses on improving hardware and network access for all students, regardless of their current digital skill levels.
2. Model 2 aims to enhance both hardware and network access while implementing comprehensive digital training and literacy programmes for all students.
3. Model 3 targets improving hardware and network access exclusively for the vulnerable group of students.
4. Model 4 combines the improvement of hardware and network access with targeted digital literacy and training programmes specifically designed for the vulnerable group of students.
5. Model 5 introduces peer mentoring and learning structures within a classroom setting, creating opportunities for students to learn from and support each other

3 Basic Simulation Model Setup

As introduced earlier, Agent-based modelling (ABM) is a computational modelling approach that simulates the complex behaviour and interactions of autonomous individual entities, known as agents, within a system (Axelrod, 1997). ABM simulation resembles a controlled experiment where various factors (or “inputs”) regarding rules of behaviours, properties of agents and environments (or any combinations of these factors) are drawn from empirical and theoretical insights, and then tested against an underlying data generating process that is likely to produce observational data in a form of simulated data from specified models. In what follows we provide a rather technical description on how those simulation models were developed and how the ySKILLS survey data have been influential in informing the model building process.

In this report, we *simulate a baseline model with 21 agents*, representing students in a classroom setting, interacting with other students in the classroom, while within the individual environments they obtain digital skills-related information based on a combination of formal learning, parental guidance, peer influence in their network, and/or any combination thereof. Then, we gradually introduce the interventions to examine their impact on adolescents’ digital skills and its distribution at the classroom level. We specify the following components to our model as a key input/setup of the model. In each of the subsequently presented simulation models, we model students’ discrete behaviours over a period of one year, treating each timepoint (“tick”) as if this is a full day of a typical

school year. Each simulation assumes 21 agents (adolescents) in their classroom, with the expected amount of social relationship (“ties”) among those adolescents equalling 21. These values were taken from the average number of adolescents across classrooms and the average number of social connections in advice-seeking relations from the ySKILLS Wave 1 network data (see e.g., [D5.1](#)).

At the onset of the simulation (*tick* = 0), agents possess initial skill levels that are randomly distributed, with values of these initial skills drawn from the normal distribution that has a mean of 31.45 and SD of 24.54, ranged from zero to 65 (these values were taken from ySKILLS W1 survey data computing mean “tech skill” levels).¹ Each adolescent also possesses a “probability of learning” and a “receptivity” parameter that respectively represent the 1) opportunity structure of learning digital skills (e.g., hardware and infrastructure, formal education, etc.) and 2) the individual-level sensitivity to skill-related education or peer inputs (representing the audience-specific effectiveness of inputs from opportunity structures). While the actual probability of learning is determined by their own digital skill level and that of their peers (see below), a random 55% of the agents are set to have a high receptivity to formal education and peer inputs ($M = .75$, $SD = .15$ on a 0 - 1 scale range), whereas 45% of the agents are set to have a low receptivity ($M = .25$, $SD = .15$ on a 0 - 1 scale range). These proportions were drawn from ySKILLS survey data showing that approximately 55% of surveyed adolescents scored improvements in their collective, self-reported digital skills over a one-year time span, whereas the rest reported no improvements (or even decline) in their digital skill levels.

Once the simulation starts, on each day (i.e., at every tick), agents interact with other agents and environments, where they may receive various influences that positively contribute to digital skill developments over time. Specifically, on each day, agents’ probability of learning (i.e., increasing their digital skills) are determined by two factors: (1) one’s own digital skill level at the current time point, and (2) the digital skill levels of one’s peers who are connected with each other. Each of these inputs assumes that the higher the input values are, the more likely a given student learns and increases their skill levels from such inputs. Therefore (by definition) those who initially score higher on their digital skills are more likely to develop even higher skill levels over time (i.e., positive autoregressive influence). In contrast, we assume network influences to be essentially random, such that agents are not self-selective about their creation and/or maintenance of social relationships based on peer’s digital skill level, as there might be a host of reasons other than one’s peer digital skill level that positively contribute to social connections among adolescents.

Formally speaking, those two inputs (i.e., the autoregressive influence and the peer-influence) are determined to take a logistic-like (sigmoid) function that maps the input values between 0 to 1 in a S-shaped curve (therefore generating two probability values). For each adolescent in the simulation it is randomly determined whether they indeed learn from environment (“*prob_learn_self*”) and their peers (“*prob_learn_network*”) by taking the average value of the two probabilities, and if this average probability is higher than a random value drawn from a uniform distribution of a mean of 0.5, they increase their skill level by the increment of 0.16 multiplied by their “receptivity” parameter (i.e., $\text{new skill} = \text{current skill} + \text{receptivity} * 0.16$). The increment of 0.16 was empirically calibrated (based on the ySKILLS data) from the average gain of skill levels divided by a one-year span among only those who showed an increase in their skill levels.

On each day (at every tick), agents also randomly change their network peers, such that a randomly drawn 20% of all possible connections are deleted and then the same amount of new ties are created

¹ Communication skill levels are very similar to these values, therefore we do not consider separate simulation based on the level of communication skills.

in a given network. This assumes a stochastic process of network change over time, yet due to the sparse nature of the empirical data, the actual network perturbation is rather modest at best.

In addition to this baseline simulation model, we add several additional setups and parameters for interventions. First, for interventions increasing the access to infrastructure and connectivity (hereafter denoted as “infrastructure intervention simulation”), we assume such interventions are likely to increase the opportunities of formal school education impacting on digital skills, albeit the specific size of the effect is rather inconclusive. Here we assume such intervention would increase the probability of learning from formal education by half (i.e., 150% compared to no intervention) for everyone in the classroom. We also additionally assume that the intervention is effective after $t > 182$ (therefore $t = 183$ or later), approximately treating a second half semester of the school year as the context of new environments due to such interventions.

Second, for inclusive access and training (hereafter denoted as “inclusive access intervention simulation”), we assume this is a targeted intervention such that it is mainly administered to the more vulnerable group of adolescents, aiming to increase the opportunities of formal school education and fostering conducive learning environments. Similar to the above setup, we assume such intervention would increase the probability of learning from formal education by half (i.e., 150% compared to no intervention) yet only for the vulnerable group in the classroom. We also additionally consider scenarios in which such interventions for inclusive access and digital equity would increase individual-level receptivity of digital skill-related inputs as well (increasing the effectiveness by half, therefore 150% compared to no intervention) yet again only for the vulnerable group in the classroom.

Third, for peer support structures, we assume this is also the targeted intervention, likely to increase the effectiveness of peer-based learning on digital skills among the more vulnerable groups. Similar to the above setup, we assume such intervention would increase the probability of learning from peers and overall receptivity to formal education and/or peer influence by half (i.e., 150% compared to no intervention) among vulnerable groups, yet the effectiveness of such intervention is further contingent upon the actual network structure and its evolution over time. For this intervention, we assume different network change dynamics, such that adolescents in vulnerable groups are more likely to accrue more social connections (hence more social support) than non-vulnerable groups.

Based on the above setups, across all scenarios, we randomly generate a total of 500 simulation runs (using different starting values) and derive mean and 95% confidence intervals for each agent’s skill levels at every time point, tracking the relative growth trajectories over time and the unequal distribution of digital skills within the classroom.

4 Results: Simulated effectiveness of various intervention scenarios

Figure 2 describe the initial conditions and their growth trajectories over time with *no interventions* applied within a given school year, where approximately 55% of agents (from A1 to A11) are set to possess high receptivity to digital skill acquisition (i.e., less vulnerable group), whereas the rest of 45% of agents (from A12 to A21) are set to possess low receptivity to digital skill acquisition (i.e., more vulnerable group). While their relative positions on the onset of the simulation are relatively homogeneous, as time progresses the gap between the high vs. low receptivity group (the latter representing vulnerable populations) increases, such that those who initially possess high digital skills are more likely to gain such skills over time much faster than those who belong to the vulnerable group. As a result, across 500 simulations, the inequality of the digital skill distribution widens over time.

Figure 3 below plots between-group components of the Gini coefficient at each time point, decomposing the Gini coefficient – a well-known metric measuring inequality and uneven distribution of the resources – into within-group and between-group components to illustrate this point further. When decomposed, the between-group components of the Gini coefficient represent the value of the between-group inequality (i.e., contribution of the group or class membership into overall inequality on the variable of interest), meaning whether there is an increasing inequality in skill distribution between the high vs. low receptivity group. As can be seen below, we see the mean value of the between-group component of the Gini coefficient increasing approximately one-half of the initial value at the end of the simulation (at day = 365).

Figure 2. STYLIZED MODEL INVOLVING 21 AGENTS

Note: Lines denote growth trajectories over a year for less vs. more vulnerable groups (baseline model)

Figure 3. BETWEEN-GROUP COMPONENTS OF GINI COEFFICIENTS

Figures 4 and 5 present the results based on the infrastructure and connectivity intervention (i.e., the opportunity structure component). In this intervention, we assume that the probability of learning is increased over time for everyone in a given classroom compared to the baseline model (i.e., no intervention). In these figures, the grey dotted line represents the reference values taken from the baseline model presented in Figure 2 illustrates the mean digital skills levels of agents grouped by high or low receptivity.

Figure 4. INTERVENTION ON INFRASTRUCTURE

Note: intervention is assumed to be effective only on the probability of enhancing self-learning, without having an impact on receptivity to inputs. Intervention effective after $t = 182$.

Figure 5. INTERVENTION ON INFRASTRUCTURE (2)

Note: Intervention is assumed to be effective both on the probability of enhancing self-learning and receptivity to inputs. Intervention effective after $t = 182$.

The results of the intervention focusing on infrastructure and access do show the expected patterns, with overall improvement in digital skills for all agents after the intervention (i.e., the second half of the school year). However, it is evident that such interventions are less likely to produce more evenly distributed skill levels across different groups with different abilities and receptivities. On the contrary, such interventions tend to widen the gaps between the less and more vulnerable individuals. While the specific long-term impact of such interventions may widely vary depending on the parameter setups in the simulation models, one point remains clear: If we assume that the interventions focusing on infrastructure may also increase the effectiveness and receptivity for everyone (instead of just increasing hardware and digital access), then the gaps between less vs. more vulnerable groups may become even wider, although their overall skill levels may still show improvement compared to no intervention – as shown in Figure 5 above.

Next, Figure 6 and 7 present the results of the intervention models focusing on inclusive access, where we assume interventions to be targeted such that they would mainly be administered to the more vulnerable group of students. As this type of intervention is first of all geared towards both equaling out “access” to digital infrastructure and learning resources (i.e., “opportunity structures”), in Figure 6 we see a slight uptake of skill levels from more vulnerable groups of individuals compared to the baseline (“no intervention”: grey dotted line), yet the degree of such uptake is rather modest under this particular model setup. This is due to the fact that merely offering access to infrastructure and learning opportunities does not necessarily increase the individual-specific effectiveness of skill-related education.

Figure 6. INTERVENTION ON INCLUSIVE ACCESS AND DIGITAL EQUITY

Note: Intervention is assumed to be effective on enhancing the probability of self-learning only. Intervention effective after $t = 182$.

Figure 7. INTERVENTION ON INCLUSIVE ACCESS AND DIGITAL EQUITY (2)

Note: Intervention is designed to be effective in enhancing both the probability of self-learning and receptivity to inputs. However, the intervention is targeted specifically towards more vulnerable groups, and it does not have the same impact on at-risk groups. The effectiveness of the intervention is observed after $t = 182$ (time period 182).

Lastly, Figure 8 describes the results of peer-support based intervention, where after intervention at $t = 182$, adolescents in the more vulnerable group were able to “catch up” with adolescents in less vulnerable groups to a comparable degree. In this model, we assumed that the peer-based intervention has a positive influence on learning from peers (i.e., network-based learning) for all adolescents in the classroom, while the intervention also increases the overall receptivity of skill-related inputs (from infrastructure and access, from formal education, etc.) among adolescents in the more vulnerable group.

While the degree of uptake in the more vulnerable group of adolescents is more modest compared to Figure 7, peer-support based interventions indeed were able to generate more evenly distributed skill levels at the end of the simulation run. Considering that the overall level of digital skill levels ($M = 67.78$, $SD = 22.64$ across 500 simulation runs) was highest in this type of intervention over other types of interventions ($M = 53.87$ for infrastructure, $M = 63.48$ for infrastructure with receptivity change, $M = 57.18$ for inclusive access, $M = 62.49$ for inclusive access with receptivity change), this suggest that increasing the receptivity of the more vulnerable group of adolescents may produce more desirable consequences, while increasing the digital skill levels across classroom more effectively than any other types of interventions.

Note: The intervention focuses on peer support structures and is designed to be effective in enhancing both the probability of self-learning and receptivity to inputs. The intervention is particularly targeted towards more vulnerable groups, but it also benefits less vulnerable groups. The effectiveness of the intervention is observed after $t = 182$ (time period 182).

Across all simulation scenarios, only interventions focused on inclusive access with receptivity change and peer-support were found to meaningfully reduce disparities in digital skill distribution between the more and less vulnerable groups of adolescents in the classroom. As shown in Figure 9, the between-group components of the Gini coefficients of digital skills increased for the other types of intervention. The intervention solely focusing on inclusive access indeed produced a somewhat

lower level of disparity between groups, yet the degree of this reduction was rather modest. This is likely due to the fact that inclusive access intervention is primarily geared towards the opportunity structure for access and learning for the more vulnerable groups, without directly increasing the receptivity of skill-related inputs. When we also consider receptivity change in the inclusive access intervention, there was an immediate decline in the between-group components of Gini coefficients, but this may mask any potential unwanted consequences (such as negatively effects on social relationships, etc.) due to the targeted nature of the intervention at the expense of other groups in the classroom. While all interventions demonstrated some level of impact in increasing digital skills for those in the more vulnerable group compared to the baseline model without intervention, it became apparent that such interventions alone do not effectively reduce the relative discrepancies in the overall distribution of digital skills. This suggests that policymakers need to be cautious about the potential consequences of interventions at both the individual and global level.

Figure 9. COMPARISONS OF BETWEEN-GROUP COMPONENTS OF GINI COEFFICIENTS ACROSS DIFFERENT INTERVENTION SCENARIOS

5. Conclusion and recommendations

This report takes a first step towards showing the usefulness of simulation models to formally model and test the potential effectiveness of intervention programmes to increase digital skills among students and to decrease digital divides between the more and less skilled students. Based on a thoroughly set up baseline model, which takes empirical inputs from previous ySKILLS deliverables (e.g., [the systematic evidence report](#)) but in particular from the ySKILLS panel data wave 1 and wave 2, the report models different types of interventions administered to a simulated classroom.

The focus was on whether interventions would lead to an overall increase in digital skills as compared to the baseline model, and in particular, whether interventions would be effectively reducing the gap between students who, at the outset, were less likely to further develop their skills (“vulnerable groups”)² versus those who would likely show increasing skill levels. The former group, the more vulnerable students, should show higher levels of skill uptake during the simulation period than the latter group, the less vulnerable students, if digital divides were to be closed due to intervention programmes. In the interventions we differentiated between such intervention programmes that would lead to an increase in access to ICT hardware and network as well as digital skills and literacy training (affecting the opportunity structure to acquire digital skills) and intervention programmes that would lead to a higher receptivity of students to actually desire to acquire digital skills. Effectively we considered three types of interventions. First, an intervention that would increase all students’ access to ICT hardware and networks as well as, in a second step, address their learning needs. Second, an intervention that focuses on increased access to hardware for the vulnerable group of students, coupled with targeted digital skills and training programmes for that particular group. And third, an intervention that promotes structures and opportunity for peer mentoring and learning in a school environment, focusing on the vulnerable group.

The simulation models clearly show that interventions that affect students’ receptivity to learning and acquiring digital skills are most successful in closing digital divides, surpassing the impact of simply improving hardware and network access. In other words, rather than investing in expensive programmes that enhance access for all or the more vulnerable students, a more effective approach is to invest in targeted structures and programmes specifically aimed at those who may not naturally develop digital skills without intervention. Such targeted interventions could include digital training and literacy programmes tailored to the needs of vulnerable students. Alternatively, a more beneficial approach for the entire classroom could be the implementation of peer mentoring and peer learning structures and initiatives. By doing so, we can effectively address the needs of vulnerable students without solely investing in hardware access, but rather by demonstrating the personal and social network relevance of digital skill.

² It should be noted that, in reality, there are host of antecedents to low level of digital skills such as poor mental health, ethnic or cultural origin, socioeconomic status and gender. Yet importantly in this report, we did not directly use such preceding factors to define “vulnerable” (or at-risk) groups but rather (consequentially) defined them based on low digital skills levels.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme for the funding (Grant Agreement no. 870612), the ySKILLS reviewers and colleagues (Leen d'Haenens, Hana Machackova, and David De Coninck) for their critical reviews and questions that helped to improve this report.

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